

**Introducing Data Driven Alarm Management to the Intensive Care
Unit of a German University Hospital**

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Abstract

Whenever the vital signs of an intensive care unit's patient deviate from values that are considered safe, staff members receive automatically triggered alarms from the bedside monitoring systems. If there are too many alarms and if the vast majority of these turn out to be false or non-actionable, staff can become alarm fatigued, that is desensitised to alarms. Alarm management interventions can help to reduce the overall number of alarms. These interventions are most effective, if they are adapted to a unit's unique situation. With this thesis, I provide the intensive care unit of a German university hospital with the foundation for a repeatable, data driven alarm management. To this end, I analyse 90 days of alarm log-data in order to create an overview of the unit's current alarm situation and to understand the way staff members are being confronted with alarms. Additionally, I survey staff members with a questionnaire that aims to assess their alarm fatigue and their approach to the unit's alarm situation. The results of both, the data analysis and the questionnaire, call for alarm management interventions that effectively reduce the number of alarms in order to ensure patient safety and ICU staff's work satisfaction. I provide suggestions for how one should proceed in implementing alarm management, as well as concrete starting points that can be used to design interventions that effectively and efficiently reduce the amount of alarms.

Keywords: Alarm Management, Data Based, Intensive Care Unit

Zusammenfassung

Die Vitalparameter von Patienten auf Intensivstationen werden automatisch überwacht. Sobald einer der Parameter auf einen kritischen oder potentiell kritischen Zustand hindeutet, wird ein Alarm auf der Station ausgelöst. Gibt es zu vieler solcher Alarme und sind die meisten davon falsch oder bedürfen keiner tatsächlichen Behandlung, kann das Stationspersonal "Alarm-müde" werden und Alarmen gegenüber abstumpfen. Sogenannte Alarm-Management Interventionen können dabei helfen die Zahl der ausgelösten Alarme zu reduzieren. Dies kann am effektivsten geschehen, wenn die Interventionen auf die spezifische Situation der Intensivstation angepasst werden. Mit dieser Arbeit lege ich den Grundstein für ein wiederholbares, datengestütztes Alarm-Management einer Intensivstation einer deutschen Universitätsklinik. Anhand der Analyse von Alarmdaten aus 90 Tagen erstelle ich eine erste Übersicht über die Alarmsituation der Station und versuche nachzuvollziehen, auf welche Weise das Stationspersonal mit Alarmen konfrontiert wird. Außerdem ziehe ich die Ergebnisse eines Fragebogens hinzu, der versucht die Alarmmüdigkeit des Personals, sowie dessen Umgang mit der Alarmsituation zu erfassen. Die Ergebnisse der Datenanalyse und des Fragebogens zeigen, dass es an Alarm-Management-Interventionen bedarf, um die Anzahl Alarme zu reduzieren und die Sicherheit der Patienten und die Arbeitszufriedenheit des Stationspersonals zu gewährleisten. Ich skizziere Vorschläge, wie man allgemein vorgehen könnte, um Alarm-Management auf dieser Station einzuführen und zeige konkrete Ausgangspunkte, die dazu dienen können Interventionen zu entwerfen, um Alarme effektiv und effizient zu vermeiden.

Introducing Data Driven Alarm Management to the Intensive Care

Unit of a German University Hospital

In an Intensive Care Unit (ICU) of a hospital, the patients' vital signs (for example blood pressure or rate of breathing) are automatically monitored by various sensors. If one of those vital signs drops below or exceeds a certain predetermined threshold, an alarm is issued to the ICU staff. Not all alarms are true alarms in the sense that they refer to a patient's situation that requires therapeutic intervention. Some alarms are false and occur due to artifacts, like bad or missing data (such as an electrode with poor skin contact, for example), other alarms are true but non actionable and hence do not require a therapeutic intervention (for example, a brief reduced rate of breathing that immediately returns to a normal rate again; Welch, 2011).

ICU staff that is overwhelmed by alarms can experience so-called alarm fatigue (Sendelbach & Funk, 2013). This involves a desensitisation to alarms which in turn can delay the response to true alarms or make a true alarm be missed altogether. Hüske-Kraus et al. (2018) argued that alarm fatigue should not be regarded as a condition of an individual, but rather as one of the whole sociotechnical ICU environment, as this allows to take a broader look at possible root causes that involves the technical infrastructure and the unit's organisation.

The noise of excessive alarms can increase the staff's occupational stress and lower its work satisfaction, concentration and overall quality of work (AAMI Foundation, 2015). On the patients' side, the alarm noise can disturb their sleep (Simons, 2018), slow recovery processes and increase their length of stay (AAMI Foundation, 2015). Alarms that are missed or responded to with delay by ICU staff can be ultimately life threatening. The Joint Commission's (2013) sentinel event database lists 98 incidents between 2009 and 2012 that are related to alarms, of which 80 resulted in a patient's death. Since reporting to the database is voluntary, this can be seen as a conservative estimate. For 2019, the ECRI Institute listed

two alarm related hazards among their “Top 10 Health Technology Hazards” (ECRI Institute, 2018).

Alarm Management as a Remedy for Alarm Fatigue

In the United States, the national patient safety goals effective January 2018 include the reduction of harm associated with clinical alarm systems (The Joint Commission, 2018). To my knowledge, there is no such official endeavour to reduce harm associated with clinical alarm systems in Germany. One project, with the aim to develop “[...] methodological and technical concepts [...] to make the load on clinical staff by means of alarms measurable and to reduce it sustainably” was founded in 2016 by the Federal Ministry of Education and Research (BMBF), but seems to have ended after the planned duration of three years (*AlarmRedux*, 2016). Alarm management, which aims to reduce the amount of unnecessary alarms (that is, false, non-actionable and technical alarms; Hüske-Kraus et al., 2018) with the assumption that this reduces the overall amount of alarms and thereby alleviates the staff’s alarm fatigue, is one way to reduce such harm. Hüske-Kraus et al. regard technical alarms as unnecessary, because although they require an action, they still could have been avoided. An observational study by Görge et al. (2009) found only 23% of all alarms to require a therapeutic intervention. And according to The Joint Commission (2013), most ICUs have false and non-actionable alarm rates between 72 and 99%. This suggests that an effective alarm management could indeed lower the overall amount of alarms in ICUs.

The literature offers many suggestions of how unnecessary alarms might be reduced. For example, it is recommended to mute alarms while examining a patient (Lorenz et al., 2017), to introduce a delay between measuring and alarming (Görge et al., 2009), to use individual thresholds for each patient instead of the monitoring device’s default (Graham & Cvach, 2010), to turn off arrhythmia alarms that are not life threatening and to change ECG electrodes and the battery in telemetry packs on a daily basis (Allen et al., 2012).

However, excessive amounts of alarms can be caused by many, potentially interacting factors, such as bad habits and workflows, a lack of discipline or insufficient training to adhere to best practices regarding threshold settings and sensor set-ups, inadequate consumables, inadequate floor layouts or faulty monitoring equipment (Hüske-Kraus et al., 2018). Given this multitude of causes, generic recommendations as the ones mentioned above do not necessarily target those that are unique to a specific ICU. Or, they might target too many causes simultaneously and with equal priority, placing an extra burden on the already busy ICU staff. Therefore, a baseline analysis of the alarm situation of an ICU can be a valuable alternative to blindly introducing generic recommendations (Cosper et al., 2017). Ideally, all potential sources of excessive alarms are analysed (Wilken et al., 2019) and a link is created between observations and underlying causes, so that specific interventions can be selected to target these causes (Hüske-Kraus et al., 2018). This baseline analysis should also be conducted in a way that makes it possible to reassess the alarm situation over time, in order to measure the effects of interventions (Welch et al., 2016).

Simply reducing the alarm rates might not be enough to change the clinicians' alarm fatigue and general attitude to the alarm situation in their unit, however (Sowan et al., 2016). By changing some of the default settings of the cardiac monitors and by re-educating bedside nurses on the use of the monitors, Sowan et al. were able to reduce the overall amount of alarms by 24% in the ten weeks following the adjustments, compared to the ten weeks preceding the adjustments. However, this did not improve the nurses' attitude towards alarms and their alarm fatigue, as measured by a questionnaire at the end of the ten weeks after the intervention. Sowan et al. saw this as further evidence that "[...] alarm management is very complex in ICUs" ("Principal Findings and Future Directions", para. 4). I would like to emphasise that, although Sowan et al.'s alarm management interventions are based on general clinical *evidence*, they are not based on their particular ICU's *data*. Therefore, conducting a

baseline analysis of an ICU's alarm situation as described above seems to be a reasonable approach to try, when planning alarm management interventions.

With the "Clinical Alarm Capability Maturity Model" Welch et al. (2016) describe the stages through which a hospital progresses, when implementing a data driven alarm management. The first of the five stages is characterised by having many non-actionable alarms for unknown reasons, approaching alarm management ad hoc and not having or not consulting data to support change. The second stage describes a situation where a multi-disciplinary team has been formed that conducts a local pilot study to understand the overall alarm situation. This can be done by analysing alarm data and surveying ICU staff. This pilot study should return a set of metrics that make informed interventions possible. The third stage is reached, once the pilot study is completed. It should demonstrate measurable reductions of unnecessary alarms and a system that allows to repeatedly collect and analyse alarm data. In the fourth stage, this system is established in the institution beyond the local pilot unit and delivers consistent metrics that indicate lasting reductions of unnecessary alarms. The fifth stage is "aspirational" and describes "[...] a sustainable culture of care where no patient is harmed as a result of inappropriate alarm settings" (p. 176).

The Aim and Structure of this Thesis

Within Welch et al.'s framework, the aim of my thesis can be formulated as to bring the alarm management of the surgical ICU of a German university hospital towards the third stage and to pave the way to create the "repeatable and sustainable system to collect and analyse alarm performance metrics" (p. 171) that is a prerequisite of stage three. Thus, my goal is to provide a building block for a repeatable, non-commercial, data driven alarm management that allows to assess this particular ICU's alarm situation and to design effective interventions that reduce the overall amount of alarms and the ICU staff's alarm fatigue, while providing the means to derive metrics that allow to track changes in the alarm situation

over time and to compare this ICU's alarm situation with that of others. I approach this project from two perspectives: an analysis of the bedside monitors' alarm log-data and a questionnaire that is handed to ICU staff. These perspectives help me formulate answers to three questions:

1. What is the alarm situation of this ICU like?
2. To what extent might this ICU's staff be alarm fatigued?
3. What alarm management interventions could be effective in reducing the amount of alarms in this ICU?

An answer to the first question draws from the results of the data analysis, where I aim to derive information about the objective alarm situation of the ICU. Here, I use the alarm log-entry data of the monitoring system, which can be accessed by the technical department of the unit. I perform the analysis without relying on commercial alarm analysis tools (which are offered by the vendor of the monitoring system, for example). This requires that the data is pre-processed in order to extract the relevant information. Finishing the script for the automated pre-processing will leave a repeatable system to build future analyses on that can also be used by other institutions using the same monitoring system.

In order to answer the second question, I conduct a questionnaire that tries to capture how much alarm fatigue the ICU staff experiences. Afterall, the data might suggest that the alarm situation is fatiguing, while the ICU staff does not necessarily have to experience the situation as burdensome.

I aim to answer the third question by taking information obtained from the data analysis together with additional information from the results of the questionnaire. The data provide a picture of the alarm situation and the staff's habits regarding alarms that allows to identify, for example, individual alarms with excessive frequencies (so-called "bad actors"; AAMI Foundation, 2015), rank sensors according to the amount of alarms they issue, find

frequent technical alarms, understand which alarm thresholds are how often adjusted by ICU staff and see what role the alarm pause function has in their workflow. The questionnaire adds information not contained in the data by asking ICU staff to identify sensors with potentially high rates of false alarms. It also tries to capture their habits in handling alarms.

Throughout the data analysis I aim to derive relevant metrics that help answer question one to three. Furthermore, metrics allow the alarm situation of this ICU to be evaluated over time (in future analyses) to see whether alarm management interventions had the expected results and to be compared with the alarm situation of other ICUs. It has been suggested, that deriving the average alarms per bed per day from the alarm data is a sufficient metric to understand the alarm burden that lies on the ICU staff or to evaluate the effectiveness of alarm management interventions over time (for example Graham & Cvach, 2010; Welch et al., 2016). But this metric can be misleading, because it ignores the alarm distribution over time, the ratio of alarms about life threatening patient conditions to other kinds of alarms and it does not inform about potential causes of excessive alarms (Wilken et al., 2019). Sowan et al.'s (2016) reduction of the overall amount of alarms, but failure to alleviate the ICU staff's alarm fatigue that I describe above, may be an example of how a reduced alarm rate should not be taken as evidence of an improved general alarm situation. It is therefore important, to collect multiple metrics of different kinds, and use them together to understand an ICU's alarm situation from as many angles as possible (compare Hüske-Kraus et al., 2018).

Hüske-Kraus et al. (2018) provide a list of prerequisites that make metrics useful in evaluating an ICU's alarm situation and for finding potential causes of excessive alarms. According to them, metrics should be practical (that is, require minimum costs and efforts to obtain), multidimensional (to cover as many contributing factors to and effects of excessive alarms), clinically appropriate (to realistically quantify the alarm burden on ICU staff), face

valid (that is, relate to the daily routine of ICU staff), granular (to allow specific analyses, such as a comparison of day and night shift alarm loads) and actionable (enable to quantify a need for interventions, find causes of unnecessary alarms or track developments over time, for example). With the metrics derived from my data analysis I try to fulfil these requirements. Practicality is provided by the fact that the data can be repeatedly accessed by the technical department of the unit and because my automated script makes it possible to easily pre-process it (the data) for further analyses. The pre-processing also structures the data such that granular analyses are possible. To fulfil the other requirements, I structure the analysis along eight dimensions: absolute alarm frequencies, alarm frequencies across rooms and beds, alarm frequencies across patients, alarm floods, distribution of alarms over time and shift, response times to alarms, threshold adjustments by ICU staff and usage of the alarm pause function. The last two dimensions focus on the habits and routines of ICU staff regarding threshold adjustments and the use of alarm pauses. The other dimensions try to measure and quantify the alarm burden from multiple perspectives and to identify starting points for effective alarm management interventions.

Methods

Approval by the Ethics Committee

Accessing and analysing the log-entry data of the ICU's patient monitoring system, as well as the use of the questionnaire is approved by the institutional review board (EA1/127/18).

Neither the log-entries nor the questionnaire contain information that identifies patients or ICU staff members.

Descriptive Data Analysis

The data consist of log-entries of events that occurred at each of the 21 beds in January and February (between 05/01/2019 03:20:56 PM and 04/02/2019 03:20:54 PM), in August and September (between 27/08/2019 11:24:41 AM and 26/09/2019 11:24:41 AM) and in October

(between 01/10/2019 12:51:39 PM and 31/10/2019 12:51:39 PM). These three samples were extracted from the Philips IntelliVue patient monitoring system (MX800, version M.00.03; MMS X2, version H.15.41-M.00.04) as CSV.

The log-entries are structured in 5 columns: “Zeit”, “Bettname”, “Aktion”, “Geräte-Name” and “Klinischer Benutzer”. “Zeit” informs about the time and date a log-entry is added to the data, “Bettname” identifies the bed the log-entry is about. “Aktion” holds information on generated alarms (the time an alarm is generated, its criticality and the value of the current threshold together with the value that was measured), terminated alarms, engaged and disengaged alarm pauses as well as threshold adjustments and other system related changes (alarm volume adjustments, daylight saving time changes et cetera). “Geräte-Name” informs about the location where the content from “Aktion” has taken place (at the bedside monitor, at a hallway monitor or in the central control room of the unit). “Klinischer Benutzer” is an empty column. The columns “Geräte-Name” and “Klinischer Benutzer” will not be used in the subsequent analysis.

Data Pre-processing

I cleaned the data with R (R Core Team, 2018) in combination with the packages “dplyr” (Wickham et al., 2015), “tidyr” (Wickham & Henry, 2017) and “stringr” (Wickham, 2010). For date and time information I used the package “lubridate” (Grolemund & Wickham, 2011). My main goal was to extract the information contained in the string of the column “Aktion” for each log-entry into new variables. Table 1 in Appendix A shows the structure of the cleaned data, followed by a link to the original R script that I used to construct it. The three original samples were extracted separately and I cleaned each of them individually, before combining them into one dataset for the analysis.

Extraction of Alarm Information. When an alarm is generated, the string of “Aktion” takes on a specific form. For example, if a patient’s heart frequency exceeds the set

threshold, the string might look like this: “***HF 135 >120 generiert um 18:09:56.” At the beginning, asterisks or exclamation marks indicate the alarm’s criticality, followed by the name of the alarm. Next to the name, the measured value of the alarm’s parameter is printed (if applicable), followed by a greater-than or less-than sign in front of the current threshold of that alarm. The greater-than or less-than sign indicates whether the threshold has been exceeded or undercut, respectively. Not all alarms are stored in this particular format. For example, alarm entries of the respirator include neither measured nor threshold values. However, all alarm related log-entries end with either the phrase “generiert um” (English: “generated at”) or “beendet.” (English: “terminated.”). The phrase “generated at” precedes the time the alarm has been issued, which is slightly earlier than the timestamp of when the log-entry is added to the data. I extracted the name of all generated and terminated alarms into a new column and added another column that specifies whether the alarm was generated or terminated.

Determination of an Alarm’s Criticality. Alarms can be a yellow, red or blue (Philips Healthcare, 2012, p. 59). A red alarm occurs in life critical situations that require immediate attention, such as apnea. A yellow alarm has a lower priority and indicates, for example that a threshold has been exceeded slightly. There is a further distinction between regular yellow alarms and short yellow alarms, where short yellow alarms are issued for rare, specific arrhythmia alarms. Blue alarms are technical alarms that occur when measurements are impeded or unreliable (due to missing ECG electrodes, for example). Technical alarms can also sound as red or yellow alarms. An empty battery of a measurement device, for example, is a yellow alarm, a disconnected ventilation tube is a red alarm.

One or two asterisks preceding the alarm name in the string of “Aktion” indicate a short or regular yellow physiological alarm, respectively. Two exclamation marks indicate a yellow technical alarm. Three asterisks indicate a red physiological alarm, three exclamation

marks a red technical alarm. A log-entry with the phrase “generated at...” in the absence of asterisks and exclamation marks is a blue alarm. Because short yellow alarms rarely occur, I will not make a distinction between these and regular yellow alarms.

Some alarms can be either yellow or red, depending on how far the measured value undercuts or exceeds the threshold. Other alarms like heart frequency (“HF”) or rate of breathing (“AF”) are exclusively type yellow, because severe limit violations are categorised as a different alarm, such as ventricular tachycardia (“VTachy”) for heart frequency or apnea (“Apnoe”) for the breathing rate.

Assignment of Alarms to Sensor Groups. I grouped all alarms according to one of 7 sensors they can originate from or as a technical failure. This grouping is based on the information provided by the manual of the monitoring system (Philips Healthcare, 2012), the medical expertise of Dr. A.-S. Poncette (personal communication, November 26, 2019) and the technical expertise of Julia Liehr (personal communication, March 21, 2019). Sensors where the cumulative frequency of alarms is less than 500 are not included in the analysis, but the individual alarms are nonetheless included in the overall count of alarms.

The respirator can issue 27 different alarms, the electrocardiogram 22, invasive blood pressure 13, intracranial pressure as well as temperature four and non-invasive blood pressure and pulse oximetry each three. All alarms with type blue criticality, as well as general monitoring device related alarms with a different criticality (such as missing patient information or low batteries) were grouped as technical alarms. All remaining yellow and red technical alarms were assigned to the sensor they originate from. Table 2 in Appendix A provides an overview of the alarms and their criticality for each sensor group.

Assignment of Log-Entries to the ICU Staff Shifts. The ICU staff operates in three shift intervals: morning, afternoon and night. The start and end time of each shift overlaps with the preceding and succeeding shift for around 30 minutes. These overlaps are so-called

hand-over periods and allow the ICU staff of the ending shift to inform the staff of the beginning shift about noteworthy events during their shift such as new patients, changed health conditions of patients, adjusted alarm thresholds et cetera. The shift and hand-over period times are kindly provided by Dr. A.-S. Poncette (personal communication, October 31, 2019; Table 3 in Appendix A). The log-entries are assigned to each shift according to the time they are added to the dataset. Log-entries concerned with alarms, however, where the time the alarm was generated at is explicitly mentioned, were assigned to shifts accordingly. When analysing differences between shifts I excluded hand-over periods due to the ambiguity of which shift they belong to.

Extraction of Room Numbers and One- vs Two-Bed Rooms. The 21 beds are distributed across 15 rooms. Each room accommodates either one or two beds. The name of each bed (from the column “Betname”) consists of the number of the room it is in, together with the letter “A” or “B”, to differentiate between beds in a two-bed room. In order to find out which room is a one- or a two-bed room, I listed the 21 unique bed names that appear in the data and assumed that every room number where a bed can have either of the additional label “A” or “B” is located in a two-bed room, while every bed that has only the additional label “A” is located in a one-bed room. According to this procedure, room one to six as well as room eight, nine and 15 are one-bed rooms. Room ten to 14 and room seven are two-bed rooms.

Extraction of Threshold Adjustments. The data stores whenever the threshold of an EEG, NIBP or SpO2 parameter is changed. The string in the column “Aktion” then takes on the form of the name of the group of parameters that is being adjusted, followed by a dash after which the name of the specific parameter together with the newly entered values are printed (for example: “SpO2 - Desat-Grenze 90”). Some grouping parameters contain only one specific parameter of the same name. This is the case with “ST”, “STE”, “QT”, “Resp”

and “Puls”. For each threshold adjustment, I extracted the group parameter name in front of the dash into a new column, which leads to eight unique parameters: “ST”, “STE”, “QT”, “Arrhy”, “Resp”, “Puls”, “SpO2” and “NBP”. According to Philips Healthcare (2012) “Arrhy” refers to advanced arrhythmia detections by the ECG and encompasses various parameters such as “Vtachy” or “VES Paar”. “ST”, “STE” and “QT” refer to segment analyses of the ECG signal and inform heart related ECG alarms. I summarised “ST” and “STE” into “ST”, because both are part of the ST-segment analysis (Sabatine, 2013). “Puls” summarises pulse measurements. Whenever thresholds are customised in “Puls”, the adjusted lower and upper thresholds are automatically taken over for the ECG heart rate thresholds (“HF”; p. 201 Philips Healthcare, 2012). “Resp” refers to respiration measurements by the ECG such as rate of breathing (“AF”) and delays for apnea alarms (“Apnoe”). “SpO2” summarises SpO2 and desaturation (“Desat”) threshold customisations. “NBP” includes systolic (“Sys”), diastolic (“Dia”) and mean (“Mtt”) non-invasive blood pressure threshold adjustments. For yet unidentified reasons, the data do not contain information on threshold changes to IBP, the respirator, Temperature and ICP. I suspect that threshold changes to the respirator’s parameters are not stored in the data, because these are adjusted directly at the machine and not via the patient monitors.

Analysis of the Data

The majority of my data analysis is descriptive. As with the cleaning, I used R (R Core Team, 2018) to analyse the data. The packages “dplyr” (Wickham et al., 2015) and “lubridate” (Grolemund & Wickham, 2011) helped me to prepare and format the data in order to create tables and visualisations. For regression analyses I used “car” (Fox & Weisberg, 2019), for visualisations “ggplot2” (Wickham, 2016).

The data span 93 calendar days but contain 90 24-hour periods. Therefore, I considered the length of the dataset to be 90 days and will hence use 90 days in my calculation of day-related averages.

Absolute Alarm Frequencies. I started by counting and visualising general alarm frequencies. Visualising the frequency of individual alarms helps to identify “bad actors” – alarms that occur much more frequently than others (AAMI Foundation, 2015). Similarly, visualising the amount of alarms issued by each sensor helps to identify which sensor should be prioritised during interventions if time is limited. Visualising the frequencies of individual alarms within each sensor further narrows the number of alarms where an intervention could lead to the greatest reduction of unnecessary alarms. I provide the metric of average alarms per bed per day.

Alarm Frequencies Across Rooms and Beds. Since the ICU has two different room types (one that accommodates one bed, and one that accommodates two) I aimed to find out whether a bed in a one-bed room produces more, less or equally many alarms as a bed in a two-bed room and whether this differs depending on the alarm criticality. ICU staff tends to assign patients that are more severely ill to a one-bed room so that they are less likely to disturb other patients by issuing alarms (Dr. A.-S. Poncette, personal communication, October 31, 2019). Thus, one might expect that a bed in a one-bed room has more alarms than a bed in a two-bed room. I report average alarm frequencies per bed per day for each room type.

Calculating Average Alarm Frequencies per Bed per Room Type. First, I summed the number of instances an alarm is generated in either room type. To calculate the average alarm frequencies per bed per room type I divided the number of alarms of each room type by the number of beds that produced these alarms. Thus, the sum of all generated alarms that are coming from two-bed rooms were divided by twelve beds, the sum of all generated alarms

that are coming from one-bed rooms were divided by nine. Lastly, for the average alarm frequencies per bed per day for each room type I divided the average alarm frequencies per bed per room type from the previous step by 90 days.

Alarm Frequencies Across Patients. The data inform about the bed where an alarm is coming from, but they do not contain information on the patient lying in this bed. It is impossible to know whether two subsequent alarms coming from the same bed also refer to the same patient, because the patient issuing the first alarm could have been relocated before a new patient issues the second alarm. I attempted to at least estimate whether the distribution of alarms across patients is similar to what Cvach et al. (2017) suggest, namely that most ICU patients have less than the average amount of alarms per bed per day while a few have more than that.

Estimation of Alarm Frequencies per Patient. I split the alarm data into 72-hour intervals, because there is a possibility that within each consecutive 72-hour subset the patients stay the same across beds. Specifically, I split the consecutive log-entries into 3-day intervals using the “cut” function from base R and assign each interval a number. Numbering the intervals allowed me to then plot the frequency of generated alarms per bed for each interval. To determine how many of the beds issue more and how many issue less than the average alarms per bed per day I multiplied the average alarms per bed per day by three days.

Alarm Flood Conditions. As outlined above, an ICU’s average alarms per bed per day can be a misleading metric. With their concept of “alarm flood conditions” Cosper et al. (2017) provide a metric that allows an additional perspective on the alarm load of an ICU and takes an acute overload of ICU staff by alarms into account. The authors define an alarm flood condition as ten or more alarms occurring within ten minutes, which according to them is more than a human operator can respond to effectively. I provide an estimate of the number of alarm flood conditions that occur in the data.

Estimation of the Number of Alarm Flood Conditions. I subsetting the data per bed and split each bed's data into 10-minute bins starting from the date-time stamp of the first log-entry. I then counted the number of generated alarms for each bin and filtered for those 10-minute bins where more than 10 alarms occur. Since each healthcare provider watches over 2 or 3 beds, the number of alarm flood conditions given by this procedure is a conservative estimate, because alarms add up across beds and create more alarm flood conditions for each individual healthcare provider.

Distribution of Alarms over Time. Cosper et al. (2017) list time of day and shift among the most useful information in alarm reports. I visualised the distribution of alarms, their criticality and their underlying sensor over an average day of the ICU. Since the unit uses a three-shift system to ensure day and night patient care, I looked into potential differences between shifts regarding the frequency of alarms.

Calculation of the Average Number of Alarms over 24 Hours. I set the seconds of the time stamp to zero, which allowed me to summarise alarms that occur in the same one-minute-bin, regardless of the date (for example all alarms in the data that occur at 2:34 PM). Dividing the sum of alarms of each one-minute-bin by 90 resulted in the average number of alarms of that particular minute across all days. Using this method, I calculated the average number of alarms of each one-minute-bin between 12:00 AM and 11:59 PM for the three alarm types and the three sensors that issue most alarms. I created two scatterplots to visualise the distribution of the average number of alarms of each alarm type and of each of the three sensors that issue most alarms. To aid the recognition of patterns in these distributions I relied on ggplot2's built-in scatterplot smoothing using the generalized additive model function $y \sim s(x, bs = "cs")$ (Wickham, 2016).

Statistical Comparison of the Alarm Frequency between ICU Staff Shifts. I tested whether there is a difference between shifts in their average number of alarms per minute.

Specifically, my null hypothesis was: “There is no difference in average alarms per minute between shifts.”. My alternative hypothesis was: “There is a difference in average alarms per minute between shifts.”. I report effect sizes as well, because due to the large number of data points I expect even small differences between shifts to become statistically significant.

Response Time to Alarms. Analysing the response times to alarms can suggest how many non-actionable alarms the ICU staff is confronted with, because staff response time seems to increase with the amount of non-actionable alarms (Bonafide et al., 2015). I visualised mean and median response times per sensor and for each of the most frequent individual alarms. Additionally, I compared the response times to alarm types across shifts.

Calculation of Response Times. I define the response time to an alarm as the time difference between the time an alarm is generated (according to the log-entries’ “generated at...” statement) and the time the log-entry of the termination of that alarm is added to the dataset (as there is no information about the actual time of termination). On average, an alarm is generated 15 seconds earlier than the time the log-entry is made. Oddly, in 627 cases (0.2% of all entries that contain an explicit “generated at...” statement) the time stated in the log-entry as the time of generation is up to 22 seconds *after* the time the log-entry is added to the data, which is logically impossible. Considering the small number of such cases this might be due to a software fault. I regard the time of the “generated at...” statement as the true time of an alarm event and as the basis for calculating response times.

To calculate the response times, I first split the data into one dataset per bed and then sort each bed’s dataset by the name of the alarm, its criticality and the time the log-entry is made. This creates a table where each row of a generated alarm is followed by the row of its corresponding termination. I then calculated the time difference in seconds between each row and the preceding row and retained only the time difference of those rows where a

termination takes place. In all other rows I reset the time difference to “NA” and re-joined the individual datasets per bed back into one dataset.

Threshold Adjustments by ICU Staff. Actively and regularly evaluating patients’ alarm thresholds can prevent many unnecessary alarms (AAMI Foundation, 2015; Bach et al., 2018; Cvach et al., 2017). For those sensors of which parameter changes are stored in the data, I aimed to assess how often staff members changed a patient’s threshold, which parameters they changed and whether shifts differed in the amount of threshold adjustments.

To achieve that, I counted the instances each grouping parameter occurs. I then calculated the relative frequency of threshold adjustments per sensor behind the grouping parameter. Because SpO2 pulse adjustments simultaneously adjust heart frequency thresholds I calculated percentages of adjustments per sensor for both cases: “Pulse” categorised as an ECG and as an SpO2 threshold adjustment. For the grouping parameters “Arrhy”, “SpO2” and “NBP”, I counted the frequency of threshold adjustments of the specific parameters as well.

Usage of the Alarm Pause Function. Another intervention mentioned in the literature that is argued to prevent unnecessary alarms is the usage of the alarm pause function during patient manipulations (Allen et al., 2012; Li & Gretzinger, 2015). The alarm pause function suspends all alarms for up to three minutes or until it is actively terminated by a staff member (Philips Healthcare, 2012). It can help to prevent alarms that would be triggered when, for example, a patient is being moved during an examination. Hüske-Kraus et al. (2018) argued that a responsible use of the pause function demands its active termination, because otherwise the healthcare provider might leave the room and thereby the patient with alarms still suspended for the remainder of the pause function’s default length. In order to understand the ICU’s habits regarding the (responsible) use of the pause function, I analysed how often pauses are engaged and how long they last before they are terminated.

Calculation of the Duration of Pauses. Whenever the pause function at a bedside monitor is engaged, the column “Aktion” of the log-entry has the string “Pause: Alle Alarme”, whenever disengaged “Fortsetzen: Alle Alarme”. I define the duration of a pause as the difference in time between the first and the second type of log-entry. I relied on the timestamp of the log-entry for both engaged and disengaged alarm pauses, because there is no other time provided by the data. The latency between the actual engagement/disengagement of the alarm pause is probably similar to the latency observed above for generated alarms.

The “Proper Pause to Pause Ratio”. According to Hüske-Kraus et al. (2018) an alarm pause can only be considered a *proper* pause if its duration is shorter than the monitors default pause duration, because this indicates that the pause has been deliberately disengaged by a staff member. Therefore, a pause running for its default maximum duration might indicate carelessness by ICU staff. The authors suggested a metric called “proper pause to pause ratio”, which is the ratio of proper pauses to all pauses. The maximum default length of the monitoring system of the present data is three minutes (180 seconds; Philips Healthcare, 2012, p. 65). Thus, in my analysis I considered any pause shorter than that duration as a proper pause.

Design and Analysis of the Questionnaire

Design of the Questionnaire

I designed the questionnaire with two goals in mind. First, it should enable me to assess to what extent the unit’s staff experiences alarm-fatigue and what habits the staff built in handling alarms (such as ignoring potentially false alarms, adjusting or communicating thresholds and pausing alarms when examining patients). Second, it should provide a way to compare the results of the data analysis with the subjective experience of ICU staff and add

information about perceived rates of false alarms. Table 1 provides an overview of the different sections and the individual items of the questionnaire.

Table 1

<i>Overview of the Items of the Questionnaire and their individual Sources</i>		
Alarm fatigue/Alarm habits: statements answered on a 5-point Likert scale ^a		
<u>Item</u>	<u>Statement (translated from German)</u>	<u>Direct source</u>
1	During hand-over periods I verbally pass on the current thresholds.	No
2	Alarm settings (e.g. alarm thresholds) are being documented.	No
3	I use the default patient-monitoring profile without adjusting thresholds.	No
4	When examining a patient, I set the alarms of the monitor on "pause".	No
5	I adjust the alarm settings for each patient individually.	Torabizadeh et al. (2017), p.1309, Table 3
6	I feel overwhelmed by too many alarms.	Ruppel et al. (2018), p. 11, Table 5
7	It happens that a critical alarm is not heard and thus missed.	Sowan et al. (2016), Table 3
8	Over time, I ignore alarms that go off repeatedly.	Torabizadeh et al. (2017), p.1309, Table 3
9	In some shifts there is so much to do that I cannot respond to alarms quickly enough.	Torabizadeh et al. (2017), p.1309, Table 3
10	Critical alarms are perceived quickly and clearly and lead to an immediate reaction.	Sowan et al. (2016), Table 3
False alarms: statements answered on a 5-point Likert scale ^b		
<u>Item</u>	<u>Statement (translated from German)</u>	<u>Direct source</u>
11	False alarms disrupt patient care.	Sowan et al. (2016), Table 3
12	False alarms reduce my trust in alarms.	Sowan et al. (2016), Table 3
False alarms: statement answered by placing a mark on a scale (from 0 to 100%)		
<u>Item</u>	<u>Statement (translated from German)</u>	<u>Direct source</u>

13 How many percent of all alarms do you think are false alarms (e.g. due to measurement errors, artifacts, wrong settings)? No

Ranking^c of Sensors^d according to the perceived (false) alarm rate

<u>Item</u>	<u>Statement (translated from German)</u>	<u>Direct source</u>
14	False alarms: Which Sensor/which device generates the most false alarms in general, according to your opinion?	No
15	All alarms: Which Sensor/which device generates the most alarms (correct and incorrect alarms), according to your opinion?	No

Note. Questions taken directly from the mentioned sources are presented here in their German version translated back to English.

^a The specific options are: “*never*”, “*rarely*”, “*sometimes*”, “*often*” and “*always*”

^b The specific options are: “*strongly disagree*”, “*disagree*”, “*Neither agree nor disagree*”, “*agree*” and “*strongly agree*”

^c The ranks are: “*most*”, “*second most*” and “*third most*”

^d The sensors available to rank are: “*IBP*”, “*Respirator*”, “*ECG*”, “*NIBP*”, “*SpO2*” and “*Temperature*”

The first ten items assess the ICU staff’s alarm fatigue and their current alarm related procedures. Because there are no standardised metrics to measure alarm fatigue so far (Winters, 2018), I constructed my own questionnaire. The items I included are either based on literature on alarm fatigue and its prevention or are taken from questionnaires that other studies developed. I define alarm fatigue in line with the definition by Sendelbach and Funk (2013), as a “[...] sensory overload when clinicians are exposed to an excessive number of alarms, which can result in desensitization to alarms and missed alarms.” (p. 378). Item 5, 8 and 9 are based on a questionnaire by Torabizadeh et al. (2017) that achieved a “very good” (p. 1308 - p. 1309) internal consistency (Cronbach’s alpha = 0.91) and test-retest validity (Spearman–Brown coefficient = 0.99). Item 7 and 10 come from Sowan et al. (2016), whose 22 items generate an internal consistency reliability of Cronbach’s alpha = 0.72. Item 6 was taken from Ruppel et al. (2018) because of its high face validity. Item 1, 2 and 4 were

included due to the finding that regularly readjusting thresholds is an effective way to reduce the overall amount of alarms (Van de Pol & Wirlds, 2017). Item 3 is based on the finding that using the alarm pause function during patient manipulations is an effective way to reduce unnecessary alarms (Li & Gretzinger, 2015).

Items 11 to 15 were meant to shed light on the alarm and false alarm situation of the ICU and to provide a new perspective on the alarm data analysis. These items ask for an opinion as opposed to item 1 - 10, which ask for the frequency of a procedure or an experience. Item 13 was included, because humans seem to adapt the frequency of their responses to their expected probability of a true alarm (Bliss et al., 1995). Item 14 adds information that is not contained in the alarm data, while item 15 can be used to compare the subjective experience of ICU staff members with the results of the data analysis.

To avoid overwhelming ICU staff with multiple questionnaires, this questionnaire was part of a larger survey that included other patient monitoring related questions from different research projects. It was sent to ICU staff both inside and outside of the particular unit of which I analyse the data. However, all participating ICU staff members are employees of the same university medical hospital and most likely use the same monitoring devices, which makes it possible to relate all responses regarding alarm procedures and experienced alarm fatigue to the situation of the particular ICU discussed in this thesis.

Analysis of the Questionnaire

I only analysed those questionnaires where respondents agreed to having their data analysed. Each part of the questionnaire was analysed with complete cases only.

Alarm Fatigue. In line with the approach by Torabizadeh et al. (2017), I included questions regarding the staff's procedures around alarms in the alarm fatigue score. Question 3, 6, 7, 8 and 9 were scored from 0 ("never") to 4 ("always"). Item 1, 2, 4, 5 and 10 were scored reversely. The summed score of the questionnaire ranges from 0 to 40, with 0

indicating that ICU staff is not at all fatigued by alarms and 40 indicating that ICU staff is severely fatigued by alarms. The midpoint of the scale is at 20 points. I report the mean, median and the standard deviation of the respondents' alarm fatigue score.

Perceived (False) Alarm Frequencies. I provide the clinician's perceived false alarm rates together with their mean and standard deviation.

For each sensor, I report the percentage of ICU staff members who perceive it as having either the most, second most or third most alarms. Similarly, I report the percentage of those who perceive each sensor as having either the most, second most or third most false alarms. Next, I deducted a weighted ranking of the sensors regarding the overall amount of alarms and the amount of false alarms. I did this by multiplying the number of respondents who vote for a sensor's rank by either 3 (for rank 1), 2 (for rank 2) or 1 (for rank 3). I then took the sum of each sensor's total weighted points. The sensor with the most points was perceived as having the most (false) alarms, the sensor with the least points was perceived as having the fewest.

Results

I report the results of the descriptive data analysis followed by the results of the questionnaire.

Results of the Data Analysis

Absolute Alarm Frequencies

The 90 days of ICU alarm data contain 297,830 generated alarms, which amounts to an average of 157.6 alarms per bed per day. Most alarms are type yellow (235,011; 79%), followed by type red (53,760; 18%). Comparatively few alarms are type blue (9,059; 3%). Figure 1 shows that the distribution of alarms is asymmetrical. A few specific alarms occur very often, while most other alarms do not. In fact, the ten most frequent alarms account for 81% of all generated alarms. Systolic arterial blood pressure alarms of type yellow sound more often than any other alarm of the unit. Yellow heart frequency alarms by the ECG rank second in terms of absolute frequency and the respirator's yellow alarms for a high rate of breathing third.

Figure 1. Total frequencies of alarms with $n \geq 500$, split by alarm type.

The alarm frequencies grouped by sensor (Figure 2) show a similar asymmetrical pattern as the individual alarm frequencies in Figure 1. Although the most common individual alarm is systolic arterial blood pressure, it is not the IBP sensor, but the respirator that issues most alarms. It alone accounts for 40% of all generated alarms. Together with the ECG and IBP it is responsible for 87% of all generated alarms. The asymmetrical distribution

is even stronger for severe, life critical alarms: here the respirator issues 68% of all red alarms.

Figure 2. Total frequencies of alarms per sensor, split by alarm type. Yellow and red alarms are both asymmetrically distributed and the proportions stay the same independent of the alarm type. For example, the respirator issues the most yellow *and* the most red alarms.

A look at the individual alarm frequencies of each sensor again reveals asymmetry in the distributions (Figure 3, 4 and 5), especially for IBP (Figure 4) and the ECG (Figure 5), where one alarm accounts for 84% and 68% of all alarms of that sensor, respectively. The most common alarm of the respirator is rate of breathing (“FREQUENZ ZU HOCH”; not to be confused with “AF”, the rate of breathing measured by the ECG), followed by the generic “OPERATOR” alarm.

Figure 3. Total frequencies of alarms with $n \geq 500$ issued by the respirator, split by alarm type.

Figure 4. Total frequencies of alarms with $n \geq 500$ issued by IBP measurements, split by alarm type.

Figure 5. Total frequencies of alarms with $n \geq 500$ issued by the ECG, split by alarm type.

Alarm Frequencies Across Room Types and Beds

On average, a bed located in a one-bed room has more alarms than a bed located in a two-bed room: 178.6 alarms per day (140.43 yellow alarms and 33.03 red alarms per day) versus 141.8 alarms per day (112.28 yellow and 25 red alarms per day), respectively. The average number of blue alarms per day is more similar between beds from the two room types: 5.16 for one-bed-room beds, 4.52 for two-bed-room beds.

Figure 7 shows that alarm frequencies also differ between rooms of the same type. Two-bed-room rooms have the higher standard deviation ($SD_{\text{One-Bed-Room}} = 2237.99$, $SD_{\text{Two-Bed-Room}} = 2837.31$), although the difference between the one-bed room with the highest and the lowest amount of alarms (room 6 and room 15, respectively) is larger than the difference between the two-bed room with the highest and the lowest number of alarms (room 7 and room 12, respectively).

Figure 6. Average number of alarms per bed per day for each room type, split by alarm type.

Figure 7. Total alarm frequencies of each room of the unit, split by alarm type.

Alarm Frequencies across Patients

As outlined above, I assume that the alarms of one bed over three days are somewhat likely to originate from the same patient. In the present data, the distribution of alarms across patients is skewed to the right. Every day on average 35% of the patients issue more alarms than the average amount of alarms per bed per day. Figure 8 visualises the amount of alarms each bed generates over three three-day intervals. Assuming that these alarms are indeed generated by the same patient during each interval it shows that in most cases two or three patients

generate a substantial amount of the interval's overall alarms. Figure 1 to 3 in Appendix B show this pattern in each three-day interval across all 90 days of data. On average 25% of all alarms in each three-day interval are caused by merely two patients. The highest proportion of alarms that two patients account for is 35% and can be found in interval 10 in January (Appendix B, Figure 1).

Figure 8. Alarms generated between January 5 and January 13 arranged in three-day intervals. Each colour represents one of the unit's 21 beds. The dashed line indicates the whole data set's average alarms per bed for three days.

Alarm Flood Conditions

In total 6,468 alarm flood conditions occur (71.87 per day, on average), of which 82% comprise between 10 and 20 alarms, 16% comprise between 20 and 40 alarms and 2% comprise between 40 and 100 alarms within ten-minute intervals.

There are five instances where more than 100 alarms occur in 10 minutes. A closer inspection of the ten minutes with the highest number of alarms (181 alarms) reveals that this is from a 20-minute period between 6:46 and 7:09 PM where in total 404 alarms are generated by the respirator of one patient. Each alarm lasts between 5 and 10 seconds before it is terminated. Something similar happens on another day between 9:25 and 11:57 AM, where the respirator of a different patient issues in total 711 alarms. In both cases the generated alarms are almost exclusively the respirator's generic alarms "ALLG. ALARM" and "OPERATOR". Another alarm flood condition with 94 alarms in 10 minutes comes from a time between 10:20 and 11:33 PM where the ECG of a patient generates in total 359 high heart frequency alarms, of which each is terminated a few seconds later. At 11:33 PM a healthcare provider finally sets the threshold of that alarm slightly higher. An alarm flood condition that comprises 153 alarms comes from a 1-hour period where a patient's ECG issues in total 252 technical alarms that inform about missing electrodes.

Distribution of Alarms over Time

On average, approximately 2.3 alarms are generated every minute across all 21 beds. The busiest minute of the 90 days entails 29 alarms, the busiest hour 562. Yellow alarms are by far the most frequent with on average 1.81 alarms per minute ($SD = 0.32$). This is more than

four times as much as the average amount of 0.41 red alarms per minute ($SD = 0.13$). Type blue alarms are comparatively negligible with on average 0.07 alarms per minute ($SD = 0.05$).

By Alarm Type. All three alarm types seem to decrease in their frequency over the course of the day (see Figure 9). The night shift generally records fewer alarms than the afternoon shift and the afternoon shift fewer than the morning shift. The scatterplot smoothing function of yellow alarms in Figure 9 reveals a wave shaped pattern with pronounced peaks in average alarm frequencies for every shift (at around 9.30 in the morning, 8 in the evening and 4.30 in the early morning). Red alarms indicate a similar, although less pronounced pattern. Blue alarms are most likely to occur in the morning shift between 8 and 11 AM.

Figure 9. Distribution of the average number of alarms per minute over 24 hours, split by alarm type. The white spaces between the highlighted shifts are the hand-over periods. Each dot shows the average alarm frequency of one minute for the specified alarm type. The scatterplot smoothing is based on ggplot2's built-in generalized additive model function ($y \sim s(x, bs = "cs")$; Wickham, 2016).

By Sensor Group. A similar decreasing wave shape can be observed in the scatterplot smoothing of the average alarms per minute coming from the three sensors that are responsible for the most alarms (the respirator, IBP and ECG; Figure 10). The function of the

respirator's average alarms per minute matches the shape of the average yellow alarms per minute in Figure 9 and seems to have the same peak times.

Figure 10. 24-hour distribution of the average number of alarms per minute of the three sensors that issue most alarms. All other sensors issue on average less than 0.25 Alarms per minute. The white spaces between the highlighted shifts are the hand-over periods. All three sensors issue on average fewer and fewer alarms over time from morning until night. Each dot shows the average alarm frequency of one minute for the specified sensor. The scatterplot smoothing is based on ggplot2's built-in generalized additive model function ($y \sim s(x, bs = "cs")$); Wickham, 2016).

Table 2

<i>Average number of alarms per minute per sensor for each shift and across shifts</i>		
Respirator		
<u>Shift</u>	<u>Mean</u>	<u>SD</u>
Morning	1.12	0.2
Afternoon	1.02	0.19
Night	0.73	0.18
Across Shifts	0.93	0.25
IBP		
<u>Shift</u>	<u>Mean</u>	<u>SD</u>
Morning	0.66	0.13
Afternoon	0.58	0.1
Night	0.46	0.09
Across Shifts	0.56	0.13
ECG		
<u>Shift</u>	<u>Mean</u>	<u>SD</u>
Morning	0.59	0.12
Afternoon	0.52	0.1
Night	0.46	0.09
Across Shifts	0.52	0.12

Note. Only the three sensors responsible for most alarms are shown.

Statistical Comparison of the Alarm Frequency between ICU Staff Shifts. The data fulfil the assumption of normality of parametric tests. The average alarm frequencies are normally distributed in the morning, afternoon and night shift (see Figure 11). Levene's test is significant ($F = 39.575$, $df = 2$, $p < 0.0001$), thus homogeneity of variances cannot be assumed. The groups' similar sizes ($n_{\text{Morning shift}} = 417$, $n_{\text{Afternoon shift}} = 429$, $n_{\text{Night shift}} = 492$) in addition to the generally large sample size make the ANOVA test nonetheless robust.

Figure 11. Histograms of the average number of alarms per minute for the morning, afternoon and night shift.

The omnibus test is significant ($F = 970.8$, $df = 2$, $p < 0.0001$), post-hoc t-tests reveal that all groups differ significantly: Morning vs. Afternoon ($t = 15.663$, $df = 737.18$, $p < 0.0001$), Morning vs. Night ($t = 39.906$, $df = 727.49$, $p < 0.0001$) and Afternoon vs. Night ($t = 30.427$, $df = 905.31$, $p < 0.0001$). All p-values were Bonferroni corrected with $p * 3$. Effect sizes are generally large. The morning and afternoon shift differ by more than one standard

deviation in their average alarms per minute (*Cohen's D* ≈ 1.1), the afternoon and night shift by two (*Cohen's D* ≈ 2.01) and the morning and night shift by almost three (*Cohen's D* ≈ 2.73). This underscores what Figure 9 and 7 indicated visually: there is a difference in the average amount of alarms between the three shifts and alarm frequencies tend to decrease over the course of the day.

Response Time to Alarms

Some response times to alarms are calculated to be unrealistically high (sometimes more than 100 hours). This seems to be due to idiosyncrasies of the log-system, where some alarm terminations are not adequately stored. In order to define a cut-off value for “unrealistic” response times I search for studies that provide maximum response times of their ICU. Unfortunately, few studies do so. Li and Gretzinger (2015) mention “technical alarms sounding for over 30 minutes” (p. 1539) and Table 2 in Bonafide et al. (2015) shows a maximum response time of 69.5 minutes. For this dataset, I will therefore take the median between 30 and 69.5 minutes as a cut-off value. Thus, every response time longer than 49.75 minutes (2,985 seconds) will be disregarded in the analysis.

Red alarms sound much longer than yellow alarms for all sensors, except for the respirator, where red alarms are terminated quicker than yellow alarms (Figure 12). Especially the ECG has a large difference between the duration of yellow and red alarms: red alarms sound on average 18 times longer than yellow alarms. Red SpO2 alarms last 6 times longer than yellow SpO2 alarms, red IBP alarms 4 times longer than yellow IBP alarms. However, a look at the median response times (Figure 13) suggests that a few extreme response time values are inflating the means of red IBP, SpO2 and ECG alarms. An even shorter cut-off value for maximum response times of 10 minutes instead of 49.75 minutes barely changed the proportions: red alarms have consistently longer mean and median response times, except for those generated by the respirator (Figure 14 and Figure 15). This

can also be observed for individual alarms (Figure 16), where red IBP alarms have the longest median response times.

Figure 12. The average response time to alarms of each sensor, split by alarm type.

Temperature and NIBP do not generate red alarms.

Figure 13. Median response times of each sensor split by alarm type. Most response times are between 20 and 40 seconds.

Figure 14. Mean response times of all response times ≤ 10 minutes for each sensor, split by alarm type. The pattern of red alarms lasting longer than yellow alarms with the only exception being those of the respirator continues even when long response times are excluded.

Figure 15. Median response times of all response times ≤ 10 minutes for each sensor, split by alarm type. Compared to Figure 10, the median response times barely change after excluding long response times.

Figure 16. Median response times of the response times ≤ 10 minutes to the ten most frequent individual alarms of Figure 1.

Response Time to Alarms across Shifts. All shifts have similar response times. With the response time cut-off at 49.75 minutes, the morning shift has an average response time of 56.7 seconds ($SD = 175$ s, $Median = 26$ s), the afternoon shift 52.4 seconds ($SD = 161.8$ s, $Median = 26$ s) and the night shift 51.5 seconds ($SD = 159.4$ s, $Median = 27$ s). A cut-off at 10 minutes shortens the average response times by 14 to 17 seconds but leaves the median response times the same across shifts ($Mean_{Morning Shift} = 39.5$ s, $Mean_{Afternoon Shift} = 37.9$ s and $Mean_{Night Shift} = 37.7$ s), which further indicates that a few extreme response times inflate the average response times. Figure 17 shows that the median response time to type red and type yellow alarms is relatively stable over 24 hours and also very similar, while the reaction time to type blue alarms is generally slower and fluctuates more.

Figure 17. Median of response times ≤ 10 minutes to alarms over 24 hours, split by alarm type. The grey areas indicate the confidence intervals of the smoothed lines. The scatterplot smoothing is based on ggplot2's built-in generalized additive model function ($y \sim s(x, bs = "cs")$); Wickham, 2016). The white spaces between the highlighted shifts are hand-over periods. The smoothed median reaction times to blue alarms have a wider confidence interval than that of red or yellow alarms because there are overall fewer blue alarms.

Threshold Adjustments by ICU Staff

Of all threshold customisations 74% are directly related to the ECG and comprise mainly adjustments of segment analyses of the signal and arrhythmia settings. The proportion climbs

to 82% if one includes the pulse adjustments of the SpO₂ measurements which automatically adjust the heart frequency thresholds of the ECG as well (Philips Healthcare, 2012, p. 201). SpO₂ adjustments account for 18% of all threshold adjustments including or for 10% excluding pulse adjustments. NIBP adjustments account for 8% of all threshold adjustments.

Figure 18 shows that most thresholds are adjusted in the morning shift (54% of all adjustments), the fewest during the night shift (9% of all adjustments). Thirty-one percent of all adjustments are done during the afternoon shift. Sometimes, thresholds are customised during hand-over periods as well, most between the morning and afternoon shift (3% of all adjustments), fewest between the night and morning shift (< 1% of all adjustments).

Figure 18. Frequency of threshold customisations split by shift with the total number of customisations across shifts displayed next to each bar. Together with the adjustments during hand-over periods the totals would be slightly higher ($n_{ST} = 10,193$, $n_{QT} = 979$, $n_{Arrhy} = 2,959$, $n_{Resp} = 825$, $n_{Puls} = 1,682$, $n_{SpO_2} = 1,970$, $n_{NBP} = 1,649$).

Figure 19. Frequency of the individual parameters that were adjusted within Arrhy (ECG arrhythmia detections), NBP and SpO2. Puls, Resp, QT and ST are not shown, because they consist of only one parameter each.

Usage of the Alarm Pause Function

The pause function is activated every day in every shift and in every hand-over period (Table 3). During shifts it is activated on average 72.6 times. Of all pauses that are started, 91% are not actively terminated but last for their default maximum length of 3 minutes and therefore do not qualify as “proper pauses” (Hüske-Kraus, Wilken, & Röhrig, 2018). The ICU’s proper pause to pause ratio is 0.09:1 and thus far from Hüske-Kraus et al.’s (2018) ideal ratio of 1, where all pauses would be a “proper pause”.

Table 3

Overview of pause frequencies per day during and across shifts and hand-over periods

During shifts

<u>Shift</u>	<u>Mean</u>	<u>SD</u>	<u>Min</u>	<u>Max</u>	<u>Median</u>
Morning	77.05	23.89	10	157	75
Afternoon	74.99	23.89	9	139	74
Night	65.86	23.81	15	138	62
Across shifts	72.6	24.27	9	157	71.5

During hand-over periods

<u>Hand-Over</u>	<u>Mean</u>	<u>SD</u>	<u>Min</u>	<u>Max</u>	<u>Median</u>
Morn. - Aftern.	5.57	3.24	1	14	5
Aftern. - Night	4.69	2.73	1	14	5
Night - Morn.	3.47	1.98	1	9	3
Across hand-over periods	4.61	2.84	1	14	4

Figure 20. Histogram of the durations of all terminated alarm pauses in 10-second bins. The majority of pauses last for the default maximum length of 180 seconds. Around 1000 pauses last between 60 and 70 seconds, which could be because 60 seconds can also be set as a default pause duration on the bedside monitors (Philips Healthcare, 2012). Approximately 300 pauses last for 10 seconds or less. Pauses are usually not terminated at 180 seconds sharp, but last for a few seconds longer (up to 187 seconds), which might be due to a latency until the log-entry was created.

Results of the Questionnaire

In total 107 ICU staff members answered the questionnaire, of which 101 agreed to having their responses analysed. Eighty-three of these 101 respondents answered every question, six respondents answered most questions and twelve respondents answered none.

Alarm Fatigue

Eighty-eight respondents completed the questionnaire's part about alarm fatigue. The average alarm fatigue score is 19.85 ($SD = 3.85$, $Median = 20$) and thereby 0.15 points below the midpoint of the scale, indicating that ICU staff experiences a reasonable, although not extreme alarm fatigue.

Figure 21. The alarm fatigue score calculated for each of the 88 complete cases. A score of 0 would indicate the absence of alarm fatigue, a score of 40 would indicate severe alarm fatigue.

Table 4

Results per Item of the Questionnaire handed to ICU staff

Alarm fatigue: number and percentage of ICU staff members who responded *often* or *always*

<u>Item</u>	<u>Statement (translated from German)</u>	<u>n (%)</u>
1	During hand-over periods I verbally pass on the current thresholds.	8 (9)
2	Alarm settings (e.g. alarm thresholds) are being documented.	8 (9)
3	I use the default patient-monitoring profile without adjusting thresholds.	16 (18)
4	When examining a patient, I set the alarms of the monitor on "pause".	26 (29)
5	I adjust the alarm settings for each patient individually.	73 (82)
6	I feel overwhelmed by too many alarms.	20 (22)
7	It happens that a critical alarm is not heard and thus missed.	21 (24)
8	Over time, I ignore alarms that go off repeatedly.	40 (45)
9	In some shifts there is so much to do that I cannot respond to alarms quickly enough.	56 (63)
10	Critical alarms are perceived quickly and clearly and lead to an immediate reaction.	51 (57)

False alarms: number and percentage of ICU staff members who *agree* or *strongly agree*

<u>Item</u>	<u>Statement (translated from German)</u>	<u>n (%)</u>
11	False alarms disrupt patient care.	68 (76)
12	False alarms reduce my trust in alarms.	55 (62)

Note. Percentages are calculated based on the number of respondents who answered the particular item. All Items are answered by 89 respondents, except for item 1 and 2, which are answered by 88 respondents.

Perceived (False) Alarm Frequencies

Eighty-nine respondents provide their perceived rate of false alarms. On average, they perceive the rate of false alarms to be 56 % ($SD = 22$ %, $Median = 61$). The highest reported perceived false alarm rate is 92 %, the lowest is 5 %. The majority of respondents agrees that false alarms reduce trust in alarms and disrupt patient care (item 11 and 12 in Table 4).

Figure 22. Histogram of the respondents estimated percentages of false alarms in bins of 5%. These percentages are given as an answer to the question: “How many percent of all alarms do you think are false alarms (e.g. due to measurement errors, artifacts, wrong settings)?”. The distribution is slightly skewed to the left: Fifty-one of the 88 clinicians who answered this question estimate that more than 50% of all alarms are false alarms.

Most respondents rate either SpO₂ or IBP as the source of most alarms (Figure 23). The weighted ranking of the sensors in Table 5 reveals that SpO₂ is the sensor perceived as having the most alarms, closely followed by IBP. ECG is on the third and the respirator on the fourth place. When asked about the source of most false alarms, the vast majority of

respondents agrees on SpO2 (Figure 24). The weighted rankings in Table 5 show ECG as the source of the second most false alarms, IBP as the third and the respirator as the fourth.

Figure 23. Percentage of ICU staff members who rated each of the six sensors as the source of most, second most or third most alarms. There are 86 complete cases.

Table 5

<i>Ranking by ICU staff members of each Sensor's (False) Alarm Frequency</i>					
Number of staff members ranking a sensor as having the most, 2nd most or 3rd most alarms					
<u>Sensor</u>	<u>Most</u>	<u>2nd most</u>	<u>3rd most</u>	<u>Weighted sum</u>	<u>Weighted rank</u>
IBP	30	23	17	153	2
Respirator	8	12	17	65	4
ECG	15	23	28	119	3

NIBP	0	2	9	13	5
SpO2	32	24	12	156	1
Temperature	1	2	3	10	6

Number of staff members ranking a sensor as having the most, 2nd most or 3rd most *false* alarms

Sensor	Most	2nd most	3rd most	Weighted sum	Weighted rank
IBP	11	20	32	105	3
Respirator	4	7	18	44	4
ECG	12	33	19	121	2
NIBP	0	3	11	17	6
SpO2	60	17	4	218	1
Temperature	1	8	4	23	5

Figure 24. Percentage of ICU staff members who ranked the six sensors according to their perceived false alarm rate, as issuing most, second most or third most false alarms. There are 88 complete cases.

Discussion

On ICUs, excessive alarms from patient monitoring devices can impair the patients' recovery (AAMI Foundation, 2015) and cause ICU staff members to experience alarm fatigue (Sendelbach & Funk, 2013), which is a desensitisation to alarms that can threaten the patients' lives (The Joint Commission, 2013). Since the vast majority of an ICU's alarms do not require therapeutic interventions (Imhoff & Kuhls, 2006), reducing the amount of unnecessary alarms could significantly alleviate the overall alarm burden on staff and patients. There are many potentially interacting causes of unnecessary alarms (Hüske-Kraus et al., 2018), which is why Cosper et al. (2017) recommend conducting a baseline analysis of an ICU's alarm situation so that specific interventions can be selected which are likely to prevent the most alarms.

With this thesis I assess the alarm situation of the ICU of a German university hospital (based on the log-data of the bedside monitors) and the extent to which ICU staff experiences alarm fatigue (based on a questionnaire). From there, I derive starting points for effective interventions that could reduce the overall amount of unnecessary alarms.

To follow the suggestions of Hüske-Kraus et al. (2018) regarding the prerequisites of useful metrics, I structure the analysis along eight dimensions, of which six measure and quantify the alarm burden from multiple perspectives and identify starting points for effective alarm management interventions (absolute alarm frequencies, alarm frequencies across rooms and beds, alarm frequencies across patients, alarm floods, distribution of alarms over time and shift, response times to alarms). The other two dimensions focus on the habits and

routines of ICU staff (threshold adjustments by ICU staff and usage of the alarm pause function). Because of the large amount of data from different seasons (winter, summer and fall) there is some possibility that the results provide an adequate picture of the alarm situation outside of the analysed period.

The Alarm Situation of this ICU

Absolute Alarm Frequencies.

The ICU has on average 157.6 alarms per bed per day. Eighteen percent of all alarms indicate a situation that potentially threatens a patient's life (type red alarms). The majority (79%) of all alarms are type yellow and indicate a situation that should be attended to, but with a lower priority than red alarms. Three percent are blue, low-priority technical alarms. With regard to the average number of alarms per bed per day, this ICU is somewhere in between what other studies report. For example, after collecting the alarm data for one day, Allan et al. (2017) report an average of 211 alarms per bed per day. Jones (2014) reports an average of 350 alarms per bed per day for one hospital and 771 for another, while Van de Pol and Wirds (2017) have 344 alarms before starting their alarm management intervention. Neither Jones nor Van de Pol and Wirds mention how many days they collected data. Unfortunately, none of these studies report the percentages of alarm criticalities.

I have shown in Figure 1 that a few specific alarms occur much more often than others. The systolic arterial blood pressure (ABPs) alarm is with 32 alarms per bed per day (on average) by far the most frequent alarm, as it occurs on average 7.6 times more often per bed per day than the second most frequent alarm: heart frequency (on average 24.4 alarms per bed per day; HF). Eighty-one percent of all alarms are issued by the ten most frequent parameters. Five of the top ten parameters are coming from the respirator. Other studies have a similar ranking of individual parameters: During their 10 weeks of pre-intervention measurements, Sowen et al.'s (2016) most frequent alarm is ABPs, closely followed by the

mean arterial blood pressure (ABPm; on average 9.8 and 9.7 alarms per bed per day, respectively). The pulse oximetry parameter (SpO₂) ranks third with on average 5.1 alarms per bed per day (8.3 in the ICU of this thesis). They do not report numbers of respirator alarms and basic ECG alarms (such as heart and breathing rate). Allan et al. (2017) find similar alarm distributions after analysing the alarm data of their 18-bed ICU for 6 days: The most common alarm is low SpO₂ (on average 33.6 alarms per bed per day), closely followed by “Art line S” (presumably systolic arterial blood pressure; on average 32.5 alarms per bed per day). The ECG alarm for high heart rate is the sixth most common alarm after diastolic and mean arterial blood pressure and (presumably technical) SpO₂ probe alarms. Taken together with the ECG alarms for low heart rate this amounts to on average 8.4 alarms per bed per day, which is low, compared to the average 24.4 heart rate alarms per bed per day of the ICU of this thesis.

My results show that the respirator is the origin of most alarms (Figure 2), despite IBP and ECG having the two individual parameters that lead the ranking in Figure 1. The respirator is responsible for 40% of all alarms and 68% of all red, life critical alarms, while IBP alarms account for 24% of all alarms (20% of all red alarms) and the ECG for 23% of all alarms (8% of all red alarms). To compare these results with those found by Allan et al. (2017), I manually assigned the individual alarms reported by the authors in Figure 2 to sensor groups and summed the frequencies accordingly. This results in 53% of all alarms being attributed to IBP, 32% to SpO₂ and 10% to ECG. Although it is difficult to compare these results, since Allan et al. do not include alarms issued by the respirator, I notice that ECG has substantially fewer alarms than SpO₂, which is the opposite of what I find in my data analysis.

The sensor groups in my analysis differ widely in the number of parameters they summarise (Temperature has four parameters, the respirator 27, for example). This makes it

difficult to compare the amount of alarms per sensor group between ICUs (as they might not use as many parameters per group) and within the same ICU over time (as some parameters might be switched off or additional parameters might be introduced). It could be that the respirator has the most alarms in the present analysis, simply because it has the most parameters of all sensor groups. I suggest a metric that weights the amount of alarms per sensor group according to the number of parameters monitored in that sensor group. In the case of the ICU analysed in this thesis, SpO₂ is the sensor group with the most alarms per parameter (3.1 alarms per parameter per bed per day), closely followed by IBP (2.9 alarms per parameter per bed per day). The respirator ranks third with 2.4, the ECG fourth with 1.6 alarms per parameter per bed per day. Table 1 in Appendix C shows the amount of alarms per parameter per bed per day as well as the absolute weighted frequencies for all sensor groups.

Within each sensor group, there are large differences in the frequency of individual parameters. Eighty-four percent of all IBP alarms come from the ABPs parameter. The two most commonly issued alarm parameters of the respirator are rate of breathing (“FREQUENZ ZU HOCH”) and a generic alarm without further specifications (“OPERATOR”). Together, they account for 49% of all alarms coming from the respirator. IBP and the respirator also feature two frequent technical alarms with red criticality. Within ECG, 68% can be attributed to the heart frequency parameter. Interestingly, 26% of the ECG alarms are coming from the rate of breathing parameter (AF), which amounts to 6% of all alarms recorded in the data, while the alarms of the rate of breathing parameter of the respirator cover another 11% of all alarms. Additionally, both sensor groups have similar amounts of life critical apnea alarms.

Alarm Frequencies across Room Types and Beds

The unit consists of 15 patient rooms that accommodate either one or two beds. A bed located in a one-bed room has 26% more alarms than a bed located in a two-bed room. A look at the alarm criticalities reveals that the room types differ most in the amount of red alarms per bed:

there are 32% more red alarms at beds located in a one-bed room (26% more yellow alarms and 14% more blue alarms). The reason for this pattern might lie in the fact that patients whose condition is worse than the condition of others tend to be assigned to a one-bed room to prevent disturbing other patients with excessive alarms or more frequent check-ups by ICU staff (Dr. A.-S. Poncette, personal communication, January 18 2019).

There are noticeable differences between rooms in the amount of alarms. For example, room seven (the two-bed room with the most alarms) has on average 160.3 alarms per bed per day, while room twelve (the two-bed room with the fewest alarms) has on average 122.4 alarms per bed per day. Similarly, room six (the one-bed room with the most alarms) has on average 213.3 alarms per bed per day, while room fifteen (the one-bed room with the fewest alarms) has on average 139.3 alarms per bed per day.

Alarm Frequencies across Patients

Since the data does not allow to identify individual patients, I estimated the distribution of alarms across patients by assuming that all alarms coming from the same bed within three days are issued by the monitoring devices of the same patient. Under this assumption the distribution of alarms per patient follow what Cvach et al. (2017) suggest: not all patients produce equally many alarms. Most patients produce fewer alarms per day than the unit's average amount of alarms per bed per day, while a minority of patients produce more alarms than that. In each three-day interval, two patients cause on average 25% of all alarms generated on the whole unit during that time.

Alarm Flood Conditions

Average alarm frequencies do not provide an adequate picture of the true alarm load that the ICU staff experiences, because bursts of alarms can be issued by individual patients during short periods of time that can overload the responsible staff members (Hüske-Kraus et al., 2018). Cospers et al. (2017) suggest measuring the acute overload of ICU staff in terms of

“alarm floods”. They define an alarm flood condition as ten or more alarms occurring within ten minutes. According to them, this amount of alarms is more than a human operator can respond to effectively.

In the data of the present ICU, on average 71.87 alarm flood conditions occur per day. The majority (82%) of the alarm floods comprise between 10 and 20 alarms, however, some floods comprise more than 100 alarms: in one such 10-minute window 181 alarms occur (which amounts to at least one alarm every four seconds). Alarm floods with that many alarms stem from longer periods of time during which many alarms are issued by one patient, such as one 20-minute period where a patient’s respirator issues as many as 404 alarms.

Bear in mind that my approach likely underestimates the true amount of alarm flood conditions that each ICU staff member experiences, because each staff member monitors two to three patients, while this procedure counts the times *one* patient generates ten or more alarms in ten minutes. If one would define an alarm flood not as happening at the patient’s bedside, as suggested by Cosper et al. (2017), but as happening “inside an ICU staff member’s head”, the alarms issued by two to three patients under his or her supervision would sum up to more than ten alarms in ten minutes much more often.

Distribution of Alarms over Time

The ICU analysed in this thesis uses a three-shift system to ensure that patients are cared for day and night. I argue that visualising the distribution of alarms over time and comparing the three shifts in their average workload creates a more nuanced understanding of an ICU’s alarm situation, as demanded by Hüske-Kraus et al. (2018).

The data show that 2.3 alarms sound every minute across all 21 beds, on average. Of these 2.3 alarms per minute, the majority has a yellow criticality (1.81 alarms), while 0.41 alarms are life-critical red alarms and 0.07 alarms are technical failures with a blue criticality. The three shifts differ greatly in the amount of alarms they experience. Most alarms are issued

during the morning, fewest during the night shift. Figure 9 and 10 show a similar decreasing wave-shaped pattern in the scatterplot smoothing function of the average alarms across 24 hours, regarding the distribution of the three alarm criticalities and the distribution of the three sensors that issue most alarms. The function of yellow alarms (Figure 9) matches that of the respirator (Figure 10) closely, which might be due to the fact that most alarms have a yellow criticality and 36% of these are issued by the respirator alone. In every shift there seem to be times when alarms frequencies peak. This is roughly indicated by the scatterplot smoothing function, where most alarms (especially those with a yellow criticality) are issued around 9.30 in the morning, 8 in the evening and 4.30 in the early morning. Blue alarms appear to most likely to occur between 8 and 11 AM.

Chambrin et al. (1999) find similar patterns: most alarms occur during the morning shift. According to the authors, this is due to more patient manipulations in the morning than in the afternoon or at night. Most technical alarms, in Chambrin et al.'s study, occur during the afternoon shift, however. Fidler et al. (2017) finds little difference in the amount of heart rate alarms between shifts. Most occur during the afternoon, closely followed by the morning shift and the night shift, which contrasts the ECG alarm distribution of the ICU analysed in this thesis, where most alarms occur in the morning (albeit the difference between the morning an afternoon shift is small).

Response Time to Alarms

The response time to an alarm is the time that elapses between when an alarm is issued at the patient's bedside and when it is terminated. Of all reaction times below ten minutes, the mean reaction time is 38.42 seconds. The large standard deviation of 54.91 seconds and the median reaction time of 26 seconds suggests a right skewed distribution with a few extreme response times and a majority of response times under one minute. Ironically, the mean and median reaction time to red alarms is slower than the mean and median reaction time to yellow

alarms for all sensor groups except for the respirator. One possible explanation for this pattern is that ICU staff focuses on treating the patient first, before minding to turn off the red alarm, while yellow alarms might be turned off immediately in most cases, because a look at the vital signs might indicate a non-actionable alarm to the ICU staff without having to rush to the patient. Alternatively, red alarms might have a higher proportion of non-actionable alarms than yellow alarms and might therefore be evaluated more carefully by ICU staff before they terminate the alarm. The latter scenario is based on a study by Bonafide et al. (2015), who find that response times to alarms increase with the amount of non-actionable alarms.

Perceived (False) Alarm Frequencies

ICU staff members estimate that 56% of all alarms they experience are false. Eight percent of all respondents believe that more than 80% are false, while only four percent believe that less than 20% are false. In estimates by other studies, rates of false and non-actionable alarms lie somewhere between 72 and 99% (The Joint Commission, 2013). With the average false alarm rate estimate of ICU staff members, the monitoring devices would have a positive predictive value (PPV) of 0.44, which is low, but still higher than the PPV of 0.23 reported by Görge et al. (2009) and the PPV of 0.27 reported by Chambrin et al. (1999). Most ICU staff members who answered the questionnaire are convinced that false alarms disrupt patient care. At least half of them agree that these false alarms lower their trust in bedside alarms in general.

According to ICU staff members, SpO₂ is the sensor group that issues most alarms, closely followed by IBP, while ECG ranks third and the respirator fourth. This ranking contrasts the results of my data analysis, where the respirator is the most frequent source of alarms. Further, in the perception of ICU staff, SpO₂ overtakes IBP regarding the source of most alarms, while my data analysis shows IBP as the source of the second most alarms,

followed by the ECG. Both sensors have almost four times as many alarms as SpO₂ (Figure 2). Temperature and NIBP are ranked as having the least amount of alarms of all sensor groups, which is in line with the results shown in Figure 2.

ICU staff members perceive SpO₂ also as having the most false alarms, ECG as having the second most false alarms, while IBP rank third and the respirator fourth. This impression is partially supported by Graham and Cvach (2010), who find that SpO₂ is the largest contributor of false alarms.

Bliss et al. (1995) find that humans seem to adapt how frequently they respond to an alarm to their perceived probability of a true alarm. Contrary to Bach et al. (2018), I doubt that this holds true in an environment like an ICU, where the patients' lives are at stake. However, ICU staff might respond slower to alarms they perceive as likely to be false. SpO₂ is perceived as having the most false alarms by ICU staff in my questionnaire, while it is also the sensor group with the third highest median reaction time in the data (Figure 15). One might argue that the fact that Temperature and NIBP are ranked as having the fewest false alarms while also having the highest median reaction time undermines the argument that ICU staff responds slower to alarms they perceive as likely to be false. However, the slow reaction times to these two sensor groups might be caused by the low urgency of their alarms. Additionally, ICU staff might not have enough exposure to Temperature and NIBP alarms to adequately estimate their false alarm rate, since Temperature and NIBP issue comparatively few alarms (twelve and 14 times fewer alarms than SpO₂, respectively). On the other hand, ECG alarms are terminated the fastest even though ICU staff perceives the ECG as having the second most false alarms of all sensor groups. These arguments are only speculative. It would require an experimental study to show whether ICU staff members indeed adapt their response frequency or response speed to how likely they think an alarm refers to a patient requiring an actual therapeutic intervention.

Estimating the Alarm Fatigue of ICU Staff

I constructed a questionnaire with ten items based on literature on alarm fatigue and its prevention and questionnaires that other studies developed. The mean alarm fatigue score achieved by the respondents to my questionnaire is 19.85 out of 40, which suggests that ICU staff experiences a noticeable, although not extreme alarm fatigue. None of the 88 completed questionnaires achieves a score higher than 27. The results of the alarm fatigue questionnaire are difficult to interpret, however, since there are no standardised metrics to measure alarm fatigue (Winters, 2018). The results do suggest that ICU staff is experiencing a fatiguing alarm overload, though – at least occasionally. Hüske-Kraus et al. (2018) consider alarm fatigue as a condition of the entire ICU, not of individuals. This approach is reflected in those items of the questionnaire, where I do not ask for a subjective experience but for a general assessment of the situation (for example item 7: “It happens that a critical alarm is not heard and thus missed.”)

Baillargeon, (2013) regards slow response times as an indicator of alarm fatigue. In this thesis, I refrain from interpreting the reaction times as indicators of a potential alarm fatigue among ICU staff for two reasons: First, I do not have adequate measurements that allow me to compare these reaction times; Second, researchers emphasise that response times to alarms can be slow for other reasons than alarm fatigue alone, such as the unit’s floor layout and policies (Wilken et al., 2019) or the staff members’ individual personality traits (Deb & Claudio, 2015). Similarly, response times can be fast for other reasons than a well-functioning organisation: ICU staff might be so annoyed by alarms that they start terminating them blindly, without properly evaluating the patient’s situation (Hüske-Kraus et al., 2018).

Interventions for Reducing the Amount of Alarms in this ICU

The alarm data suggests that the bedside monitors of this particular ICU issue an excessive number of alarms in patterns that are likely to overwhelm ICU staff members on shift. The results of the questionnaire show that ICU staff members of this university hospital are to some extent fatigued by alarms and indicate that more than half of these alarms are potentially false. Additionally, the data show many alarms are technical alarms, which Hüske-Kraus et al. (2018) regard as unnecessary a priori. All in all, these results call for alarm management interventions that effectively reduce the overall number of alarms in order to ensure patient safety and ICU staff's work satisfaction.

General Procedure

Effective alarm management ultimately relies on motivated and participating ICU staff members. For alarm management interventions to be adhered to in the long run and to noticeably reduce the objective amount of alarms as well as the subjectively perceived alarm burden by ICU staff, these interventions need to be carefully selected, implemented and monitored. I believe that asking ICU staff to suddenly follow new rules and establish new routines can be detrimental to the long-term success of alarm management if these rules are not carefully thought through, turn out to be ineffective and thereby reduce ICU staff's trust in new interventions. Before asking ICU staff to follow new interventions, I suggest collecting more information that helps to derive interventions that require the least amount of effort by ICU staff members while being maximally effective in reducing the overall amount of alarms. Figure 25 provides an overview of the general procedure that I recommend.

In my opinion, there is even more valuable information to gain from the data than I presented in this thesis. In order to find out whether the upper or lower heart frequency (HF) threshold should be prioritised in threshold adjustments, I suggest splitting the parameter to see how many alarms were issued because the patient's value exceeded the upper limit and

how many were issued because he or she undercut it. Ideally, this differentiation is made for all parameters that rely on upper and lower thresholds, but heart frequency is the second most frequent alarm and should be targeted first. Next to that I suggest making exact per bed alarm analyses for beds in two-bed rooms. This would show whether some beds issue more alarms than others (information that is lost in my approach, where I average the alarm frequency across the two beds of two-bed rooms) and help understand the alarm situation in a more detailed manner. Although they do not explicitly discuss it, Van de Pol and Wirds (2017) show a Figure where they investigate the frequency that each specific SpO₂ and ABPs threshold is crossed (page 3, on the left-hand side). This can help to understand, whether a small change to the parameter's default threshold could prevent most of its alarms. This information can be derived from the data of this thesis as well and I recommend making use of it. Lastly, with regard to further data analyses, I suggest searching for unnecessary alarms "bottom up". While the ten most frequent alarms in Figure 1 account for 81% of all alarms, there are numerous parameters that occur less frequently but jointly contribute a substantial amount of alarms. For example, a parameter that issues an alarm 270 times in total across 90 days might seem insignificant at first. However, this corresponds to one alarm per shift every day, on average. Specifically searching for sparse alarms in the data can help to find those that are potentially preventable.

I suggest making an inventory of the current criticalities of the technical and physiological alarms, as well as the current default thresholds and alarm reminder settings. The first type of inventory can help to reconsider the parameters' criticalities (which is technically possible; Philips Healthcare, 2012) and thereby reduce the noise that ICU staff is confronted with. The second type can help in reconsidering the default thresholds of some parameters and to decide whether or not to set up a delay of a few seconds between the detected threshold violation and the alarm issuing, for certain parameters (the bedside

monitors offer this possibility; Philips Healthcare, 2012). Many studies have shown that introducing a delay between measuring and alarming can lower the amount of alarms (for example: Görges et al., 2009; Pater et al., 2020). Carefully reconsidering the default thresholds of the monitoring devices has the potential to prevent many alarms, as 18% of ICU staff members who responded to the questionnaire admit relying solely on the monitors default threshold settings. According to Philips Healthcare (2012, page 65) the monitors can be configured to issue an “alarm reminder”, which repeats the auditory and visual signal of the original alarm after the original alarm has been terminated (if the alarming condition of the patient persists). This reminder can be set up to continue indefinitely. I recommend checking whether such a reminder configuration is present and if so, how long it takes until a reminder is issued and for how long it is sustained, as these factors can increase the unit’s noise level and contribute to the staff’s alarm fatigue. I also recommend assessing the ICU staff’s competencies regarding tasks that are likely to prevent many alarms. For example, it would be valuable to know, whether the 18% who admit to exclusively using the default threshold settings do so, because they do not know how to adjust the thresholds on the monitoring devices.

Knowing which of the ICU staff’s skills are absent or could be improved would allow to design specific trainings before implementing interventions. Additionally, one could consider to train “monitor superusers” which are ICU staff members who volunteer to become experts on setting up the monitoring devices and help their colleagues during shifts (Sowan et al., 2016). Sowan et al., who use the same monitoring devices as the ICU subject to this thesis, conclude that “the complexity of these monitors require [*sic*] interactive, well-designed, and periodic training.” (Principal Findings and Future Directions, para. 5). Sowan et al. (2017) emphasise the need for “monitor superusers” and devise a list of competencies for the use of monitoring devices, that could be used to assess the skills of the staff members

of the ICU of this thesis. When implementing interventions, I recommend pre- and post-analyses of the alarm data (ideally combined with a pre- and post-intervention survey) in order to track their effectiveness.

Figure 25. Outline of the general procedure that I recommend for advancing the alarm management of the ICU discussed in this thesis. The recommendations progress according to the estimated effort that is required to realise them. Most of the work is preparatory and

consists of additional data analyses, inventories of the current default settings of the monitoring devices and an assessment of staff competencies.

Concrete Interventions

In Figure 26 I summarise concrete starting points of interventions that are likely to be effective while requiring comparatively little extra work. In the data analysis and in the questionnaire, I try to assess to what extent and in which way ICU staff already practices habits that are known to prevent unnecessary alarms. These include threshold customisations (Graham & Cvach, 2010), using the pause function while examining the patient (Lorenz et al., 2017) and documenting patients' thresholds (Allen et al., 2012). According to the results of the questionnaire, the majority of ICU staff is already used to adjusting patients' thresholds, as 82% of all respondents state to adjust these regularly. Therefore, concentrating or shifting their efforts of choosing appropriate thresholds to the most frequent parameters in particular could prevent many alarms. According to the data, ICU staff adjusts thresholds mainly during the morning shift. Maybe even more alarms could be prevented, if the thresholds of the ten, five or three most frequent parameters (depending on what the schedule and workload allows) are discussed in each hand-over period and if thresholds are as often customised in the afternoon shift and the beginning of the night shift as they are in the morning shift.

The data shows that a 6% and 11% of all alarms are coming from the ECG's parameter for breathing rate (AF) and the respirator's parameter for breathing rate (FREQUENZ ZU HOCH), respectively, and that both sensor groups have similar amounts of life critical apnea alarms. Maybe there are instances, where both parameters are enabled simultaneously for a patient. Since both parameters measure the same physiological event, ICU staff might prevent many alarms by setting up only one of the two parameters to alarm

about abnormal breathing rates (if clinically appropriate). Solet and Barach (2012) recommend finding similarly redundant alarms throughout the set-up in general. After constructing the inventories as I suggest in Figure 25, more such redundancies could be found, when studying the inventory together with the alarm data.

The most common technical alarm on the ICU discussed in this thesis is due to missing ECG electrodes. Proper skin preparation and a daily replacement of ECG electrodes has been repeatedly shown to reduce missing electrode alarms as well as other ECG alarms by up to 74% (Cvach et al., 2013; Shue McGuffin & Ortiz, 2019; Walsh-Irwin & Jurgens, 2015). The second most frequent technical alarm in this unit is issued by the respirator, the third and fourth most frequent technical alarm by IBP. Unfortunately, I am missing the clinical expertise to pinpoint possible causes of these alarms and devise concrete recommendations. However, they should be highlighted and discussed with ICU staff, since they are likely preventable.

The data show that ICU staff is using the pause function, which suspends all alarms for up to three minutes, on a daily basis. Ideally this function is used while patients are manipulated to prevent movement induced alarms (Lorenz et al., 2017), however, in the questionnaire only 29% of ICU staff members state to use it that way. Therefore, I suggest to briefly remind ICU staff of using the pause function during patient manipulations. It is possible that ICU staff is not aware of the pause function or does not know how to engage it. This should be assessed when conducting inventories, as suggested in Figure 25. In the data, most pauses last for their default maximum length of three minutes, which might point towards a carelessness of ICU staff, according to Hüske-Kraus et al. (2018), who argue that pauses should be terminated manually to ensure patient safety. Therefore, ICU staff should not only be reminded of using the pause function but also of using it properly.

1. Make frequent threshold adjustments to the top ten alarm parameters.

Respirator: *FREQUENZ ZU HOCH, OPERATOR, PEEP VERLUST*
and *MINVOL ZU TIEF*

IBP: *ABPs* and *ABPm*

ECG: *HF* and *AF*

SpO₂: *SpO₂*

- ❖ Consider to make it a habit to discuss the thresholds of these high frequency alarms during hand-over periods.

2. Check whether breathing rate is monitored by the respirator and ECG simultaneously.

- ❖ If so and if clinically appropriate, consider switching off either one.

3. Check for preventable, frequent technical alarms.

- ❖ Make sure that ECG lead electrodes are applied with proper skin preparation. Consider switching these electrodes daily.
- ❖ Watch out for potential causes of the alarm for the patient being disconnected from the respirator (*DISKONNEKT.PAT*)
- ❖ Prevent IBP missing pressure alarms (*ABP BEREICH?*) and IBP connectivity losses (*ABP unterbrochn*)

4. Remember to use the alarm pause function during patient manipulations.

- ❖ Consider to remind of the pause function during hand over periods.
- ❖ Make sure to switch off the alarm pause after manipulating the patient or to re-enable it, if more time is needed.

Figure 26. Outline of starting points for concrete interventions that can be derived from the results of the data analysis and the questionnaire. These suggestions should be reviewed carefully by a multidisciplinary team that combines technical and clinical expertise, before being implemented and taken into consideration when preparing interventions as outlined in *Figure 25.*

Limitations

Some of my procedures in conducting the data analysis and the questionnaire might limit the reliability and validity of the results I presented. For example, when calculating the average alarms per bed per day and the average alarms per room, I rely on the total bed count, which might involve unoccupied beds as well, while Cosper et al. (2017) recommend using only the number of truly occupied beds for these metrics. Or, researching for how long patients stay on the ICU on average would have allowed me draw more sound conclusions regarding the alarm frequency per patient, than simply assuming it is 72 hours.

It is possible that an alarm is stored in the data as “terminated” if it stopped on its own after the measured value returns below the threshold (which is the default setting, unless the alarm reminder function turned on; Philips Healthcare, 2012). If alarms are indeed stored as terminated in such cases, “alarm duration” would be a more adequate term than “response time”, since the latter implies that an ICU staff member actively terminated the alarm.

Another limitation related to the response times is that I cannot explain why some response times are several hours long (the longest response time is over 500 hours). I verified that these are not calculation errors of the script that I used to derive them, by manually recalculating the 6 most extreme response times. Additionally, I manually checked the response times of 50 random other alarms – all were correctly calculated by the script.

My way of deriving an estimate for the amount of alarm flood conditions is somewhat limited by the fact that I start splitting the data into ten-minute bins starting from the first log entry. Applying another template of binning will likely change the number of alarm flood conditions. However, I believe that my approach gives the best estimate nonetheless, because it ensures that all data points are taken into account. Other binning methods would either create overlap between bins or leave out data points.

Two drawbacks of the questionnaire and the way I implemented it limit my ability to draw firm conclusions from its results. First, it is not properly validated, except by its face validity. Second, the questionnaire was part of a larger survey that included other alarm related questionnaires from different research projects and was sent to ICU staff both inside and outside of the particular unit of which I analyse the data. Therefore, the responses cannot be directly linked to it. However, all participants are ICU staff members of the same university medical hospital and most likely use the same monitoring devices.

Finally, the biggest limitation of my recommendations is that I am neither clinically educated nor do I know much about the current procedures on the present ICU. However, as I outlined above, I consider this thesis to be mainly a starting point for a multidisciplinary conversation about feasible alarm management interventions.

Conclusion

My thesis constitutes an initial building block for a repeatable, non-commercial, data driven alarm management for the ICU of a German university hospital. I tried to show what the alarm situation of this ICU is like, to understand the extent to which ICU staff might be alarm fatigued and to derive starting points for effective alarm management interventions. To this end, I conducted a descriptive data analysis of the alarm log-data of the bedside monitoring devices and issued a questionnaire to ICU staff. The alarm data shows that a few parameters are responsible for the majority of alarms on this ICU. Most alarms are issued during the morning shift and by patients in one-bed rooms. The respirator issues the most alarms by far, followed by IBP and the ECG. It seems that during a three-day period, usually two or three patients issue many more alarms than the average amount of alarms per bed per day. At times, ICU staff is confronted with more than one alarm per minute, making it impossible to respond adequately to them. The questionnaire indicates that ICU staff is fatigued by this alarm situation. They estimate that at least half of all alarms are false and that these false

alarms disrupt patient care. To reduce the overall amount of alarms it is necessary to design effective alarm management interventions. To do so, I suggest further data analyses, inventories of the current monitoring settings and an assessment of ICU staff's expertise in setting up patient monitoring. Concrete interventions to consider are focussing threshold adjustments on highly frequent alarm parameters first, tracing redundant alarms, finding the causes of the most frequent technical alarms and using the alarm pause function properly.

All interventions as well as their results should be regularly communicated to ICU staff. Afterall, alarm management can only be effective if ICU staff members are motivated to participate, since most interventions rely on their willingness to adopt new or altered behaviours and procedures.

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Appendix A

Table 1

<i>Structure of the final dataset that is used for the analysis</i>		
<u>Variable</u>	<u>Information</u>	<u>Class</u>
Zeit	Time and date of the log-entry	POSIXct
Bettname	Name of the bed that the log-entry is about	Factor
TrueTime	The time and date an alarm is generated	POSIXct
Alarm	The name of the alarm that is generated or terminated	Factor
Situation	Specifies whether an alarm is generated or terminated	Factor
Zeitdifferenz	Time difference between the generation and termination of an alarm in seconds	Numeric
Alarmfarbe	Alarm criticality (red, yellow or blue)	Factor
Alarmgruppe	The sensor that generates the alarm	Factor
Alarmpause	Activation or deactivation of the alarm pause function	Factor
PausenDauer	Time difference between activation and deactivation of the alarm pause in seconds	Numeric
Schicht	The shift or hand-over period where a log-entry is generated	Factor
Bettenanzahl	Whether the bed a log-entry is about is located in a one- or two-bed room	Factor
Grenzwert	Which parameter's threshold is adjusted, or which parameter is switched on or off	Factor
Zimmernummer	The room of the bed the log-entry is about	Numeric

Note. POSIXct is the date-time class of the R programming language.

The Script Used to Clean the Data

<https://github.com/ogelosgehts/AlarmDataCleaning>

Table 2

<i>Overview of alarms and their criticality contained in each sensor group</i>	
Respirator	
<u>Criticality</u>	<u>Alarm</u>

Yellow	APNOE VENTILAT. ^a , CO2 TIEF/HOCH, DRUCK TV LIMIT, FREQUENZ ZU HOCH, OPERATOR, PEEP VERLUST, TV HOCH, TV NICHT KONST.
Red	AFaw HOCH, ALLG. ALARM, APNOE, awP HOCH, awP NIEDRIG, DISKONNEKT. PAT, DISKONNEKT. VENT, DRUCK ZU HOCH, FIO2 HOCH ^a , FIO2 NIEDRIG ^a , FIO2 TIEF/HOCH, GASVERSORGUNG, MinVol HOCH, MinVol NIEDRIG, MINVOL ZU HOCH, MINVOL ZU TIEF, PEEP HOCH, SPO2 TIEF/HOCH, TV HOCH, VENT SCHLAUCH? ^a

Electrocardiogram

<u>Criticality</u>	<u>Alarm</u>
Yellow	AF, AFIB, EndeUnregelm.HF, HF, HF unregelmäßig, Multiform VES, Paroxysmale VT, Pause, QRS ausgelassen, ST I, VES Paar, VES Salve Hoch, VES/min
Red	Apnoe, Apnoe > 10min, Asystolie, Vent ALARM ^a , Vent Fib/Tachy, Vent STANDBY ^a , VTachy, xBrady, xTachy

Invasive Blood Pressure

<u>Criticality</u>	<u>Alarm</u>
Yellow	ABPd, ABPm, ABPs, PAPs, UAPs
Red	ABP Bereich? ^a , ABPd, ABPm, ABPs, ABPunterbrochn, ART Bereich? ^a , ARTunterbrochn, P Bereich? ^a , PAP Bereich? ^a , PAPs, PAPunterbrochn, UAP Bereich? ^a

Intracranial Pressure

<u>Criticality</u>	<u>Alarm</u>
Yellow	CPP, ICPm, ICPs
Red	ICP Bereich? ^a , ICPm

Temperature

<u>Criticality</u>	<u>Alarm</u>
Yellow	TBlut, Temp, THaut, TKern
Red	–

Non-Invasive Blood Pressure

<u>Criticality</u>	<u>Alarm</u>
Yellow	NBPd, NBPm, NBPs

Red	–
Pulse Oximetry	
<u>Criticality</u>	<u>Alarm</u>
Yellow	Puls, SpO2 ^b
Red	Desat
Technical Failure	
<u>Criticality</u>	<u>Alarm</u>
Blue	AkkErw fehlt, AkkErw schwach, Akku schwach, EKG Elektrdn ab, Fehler Akku Erw., MSL Verbindung?, SL Verbindg prüfn
Yellow	AkkErw leer, Akku einlegen, Akku leer, Pat. ID überprüf
Red	–

Note. The following alarms were not assigned to sensor groups, because the cumulative frequency of their sensor group would be <500: ZVD Bereich?^a, ZVDs, ZVDm, etCO₂, BIS, Ps, awAF and kHI.

^a Technical alarm of the given sensor.

^b I summarise SpO_{2r}, SpO_{2l} and SpO₂ into one SpO₂ parameter.

Table 3

<i>Schedule of the morning, afternoon and night shift and the hand over periods in between</i>	
<u>Shift</u>	<u>Scheduled Time</u>
Morning	6:36 AM to 2:42 PM
Hand-over Morning- Afternoon	2:06 PM to 2:42 PM
Afternoon	2:06 PM to 10:24 PM
Hand-over Afternoon-Night	9:51 PM to 10:24 PM
Night	9:51 PM to 7:09 AM
Hand-over Night- Morning	6:36 AM to 7:09 AM

Appendix B

Figure 1. Alarms generated in January and February arranged in three-day intervals. Each colour represents one of the unit's 21 beds. The dashed line indicates the whole data set's average alarms per bed for three days.

Figure 2. Alarms generated in August and September arranged in three-day intervals. Each colour represents one of the unit's 21 beds. The dashed line indicates the whole data set's average alarms per bed for three days.

Figure 3. Alarms generated in October arranged in three-day intervals. Each colour represents one of the unit's 21 beds. The dashed line indicates the whole data set's average alarms per bed for three days.

Appendix C

Table 1

Alarm frequencies for each sensor group, weighted by the group's number of parameters

<u>Sensor group</u>	<u>Parameters used^a</u>	<u>Weighted rank^b</u>	<u>Alarms/parameter/bed/day</u>
SpO2	3	5,876	3.1
IBP	13	5,559	2.9
Respirator	27	4,458	2.4
ECG	22	3,071	1.6
ICP	4	1,917	1.0
Technical Failure	11	839	0.4
NIBP	3	418	0.2
Temperature	4	361	0.2

^a The number of unique parameters that appear in the data, not the theoretically possible number of parameters that could be monitored, as shown in Table 2, Appendix A.

^b Calculated as the absolute frequency of alarms per sensor group divided by the number of parameters summarised by that sensor group and rounded to the nearest whole number.